

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract: In these modern days, the whole world has become a global village and people communicate with each other in a common language, English.

Key words: English, internet, IT

The English language is spoken all over the world and it has attained the status of the global language. English is the language widely used in the field of scientific research, education, business, the internet, travel and tourism, media and newspapers, software, medicine, engineering, information and technology, entertainment, banking and so on. English is the language that is used mostly for business correspondence and internet purposes. It is the only major language used in writing scientific research articles as more than 85% of the research publications are in English. It is the international language used for trade and commerce. Even in the IT field also, most of the programmes are written in English and even they communicate with their colleagues or other software professionals those who work around the world in English. As English serves the purpose of international communication, most of the foreign language learners try to learn it. In this process, they have to acquire all the four basic skills of the language, viz. listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and reading are passive skills or receptive skills, whereas, speaking and writing are active skills or productive skills.

Fig: The Basic Language Skills of English

Speaking skill is the most important skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Among the four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important skill in learning a foreign or second language. Brown and Yuke (1983) say, "Speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real life situations". Regardless of its importance, teaching speaking skills have been undervalued and most of the EFL/ESL teachers have been continuing their teaching of speaking skills just as memorization of dialogues or repetition of drills. Nevertheless, the modern world demands for the requirement of communication skills for the learners and the English teachers have to teach the ELLs the needed skills so that they will improve their abilities in speaking and perform well in real-life situations. In the present EFL/ESL teaching environment, oral skills are completely neglected whereas employability depends more on communication

than technology. As very less priority has been given to the important elements of language such as phonological, morphological, semantic and syntactic aspects, it has become a major impediment for the ELLs to acquire the speaking skills among the learners of English. So far, more concentration has been given to reading and writing skills. After realizing the importance of oral communication skills, more emphasis is now laid on developing the speaking skills of the learners to pursue their studies successfully and excel in their fields once they finish their education. Moreover, English is the language of getting opportunities for employment and getting success to achieve the desired goals in life. Speaking skills are the most important skills for ELLs as they are very useful for them in exhibiting their communication skills for various purposes. Hence, the teachers have to take a special interest in improving the speaking skills of the ELLS. For this purpose, the teachers have to refer to the latest material related to and try to adopt several techniques and approaches to develop the speaking skills of the learners in the English classrooms. The teachers should also choose appropriate material suitable for the level of the learners.

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